

The Problems with Doctoral Degrees in Pakistan, with a Focus on PhD in English: A Question of Quality Assurance

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Abstract

This study aimed at identifying potential concerns and problems of PhD programs in Pakistan. It attempted to assess the value of doctoral programs in English. The main reasons and problems associated to the PhD programs and specially to PhD in English are lack of highly qualified personnel, ill-equipped labs, less financial support, unnecessary delays in research, low and narrow mindedness of research supervisors, lack of the availability of foreign faculty, too much stress on the theoretical and course work. Moreover, insufficient internet access, lack of collaboration with international universities and discordance with the national demands. The survey questionnaires employed in this research study confirmed the agreement of the research respondents` that the issues and problems were far higher than the disagreement ratio.

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Introduction

The Higher Education Commission (HEC) since its inception in 2002 has been focusing on increasing the number of Ph.Ds. in Pakistan. New scholarship opportunities, both foreign and indigenous have been made more widely available since then. More money was set allocated for research projects, and research grants were made available to present papers in international conferences. In addition, the HEC also offered chances for higher education institutions to hire highly qualified faculty. Consequently, a high number of students are enrolling in Ph.D. programs to get ready for university teaching and research jobs. Therefore, many universities have started offering doctoral programs in different disciplines. Though these developments in higher education are admirable but without adequate preparation, funding and other issues in the PhD programs make the programs less productive in real sense.

The HEC has introduced stringent measures to ensure the quality of higher education and particularly PhD programs. The HEC strictly monitors Ph.D. programs which requires universities to follow the HEC's guidelines to maintain their minimum quality.

In addition to these issues, the final research thesis plays a critical role in the Ph.D. Programs. As a result, in a good doctoral research program, the research supervisor and scholar working relationship is critical. However, unfortunately, in many Pakistani universities, this relationship is not very strong because supervisors take many Ph.D. students for honorarium and this results in compromise on quality. Another reason of the poor quality is that scholars choose supervisor-selected study topic rather than the one that interests them. Furthermore, due to a severe workload of other monitored students, the supervisor is unavailable to the scholar, resulting in inefficiency and quality assurance failures. Despite their best efforts, such supervision concerns cause an interminable delay in students' thesis completion.

The purpose of this research study was to determine the efficacy, strengths, and flaws of English Ph.D. degree programs in Pakistan, to assess the reasons for its failure and to present suggestions to improve the doctoral programs' efficacy. Thus the following questions guided this study:

1. What are the most typical issues in Pakistani English Ph.D. programmes?
2. What are the main causes of poor quality of Pakistani PhD English programs?
3. What should be done to raise the quality of Pakistan English PhD programs?

Literature Review

Universities across the world are re-organizing their Ph.D. programs in order to improve their worth and in order to be fully compliant with today's rapidly changing world, universities must review their traditional activities. There are factors like teaching, research, development of skills, enhancement of knowledge and

management which need to be focused for initiating higher degree programs. The Ph.D. degree has always been regarded as a sign of advanced study and excellence in research methodology in academic circles. It is also a necessary component of worldwide competitiveness (Knight and De Wit, 1997; Scott, 1998; Marginson, 2001). It is assessed based on its research training, supervision, authenticity, and/or quality and standards. Academics have a lot of criticisms for Ph.D. programmes.

Academics and students have written numerous critical reviews of Ph.D. programmes, questioning the usefulness of a doctoral degree's learning experience (Delamont et al, 2000; Hoad, 2000; Hoddell et al, 2002; Lewis, 2002; Murray, 2002; Plomin, 2001a, 2001b; Tinkler and Jackson, 2002; Wakeford, 2000,2001). Students and companies in the United Kingdom and other nations have recently questioned the PhD qualification's suitability. Doctoral programmes are increasingly being criticized by governments, financial authorities, and higher education institutions (Anon., 2002). Roberts Report (2002) states that institutions which do not respond enough to change student experiences or prepare students for employment outside of academia.

With the passage of time, several opinions on the PhD degree have emerged. They are known as "teaching at degree" by Mitchell (2002), and thus, a research mission is made moving forward and many academics switch their responsibilities. The dispute over the value of a doctoral degree isn't new, and it's not limited to one country. Doctoral programmes are a source of concern.

The dispute over the value of a doctoral degree isn't new, and it's not limited to one country. Even in the world's most developed countries, questions about PhD programs arise from time to time. Many North American Ph.D. programs, according to Cude (1987), are inflexible, onerous, restricting, and inefficient. Doctoral programs in numerous areas have become traps for candidates and sinkholes for intellectual resources (Cude, 2001)

Methodology

A ten-question survey was established to know the assumptions of the English PhD program in Pakistan, using responses from MS and PhD students in applied linguistics at the University of Management and Technology, UMT, Lahore. The responders for the said program came from all throughout the country; hence there was a wide range of responses.

The questionnaires were presented to 40 students in the English Department (male and female). There were just 33 questions that were returned. The goal of the research survey was to learn what these students thought about the quality and challenges of obtaining a PhD in English in Pakistan. Many of the students had prior experience with, and even reservations about, the PhD Programme. The majority were teachers from various colleges and universities.

Figure: Lickert Scale Data of the Questionnaire Survey Items Regarding the PhD Programmes in Pakistan
 The ten-item based questionnaire survey was given to respondents who were students at the Department of English, UMT, Lahore, and who came from various parts of the country, as described above. The ratio of Strong

disagreement, disagreement, neutrality, agreement, and strong agreement statements is shown in Figure 1. Looking at the data in the graph above, the majority of respondents agreed with the item of our country's PhD compatibility with the rest of the world, with a ratio of 10 out of 33, but other parts of the items were very lightly discussed. In response to the second question, 20 out of 33 respondents strongly agreed that libraries are important for research and PhD programmes, and that net connection availability for the maximum amount of time is important, with 23 out of 33 respondents strongly agreeing. The majority of the research participants agreed that a PhD faculty member was required. Thirteen out of 33 respondents agreed that international professors should be hired and that foreign staff are better suited for PhD programmes in Pakistan. However, 19 out of 33 participants believed that the most significant aspect in the supervisor-supervisee relationship was also crucial, and that awarding scholarships for further education was also important. Inter university harmony was also regarded for effective and smooth operation of the doctoral programmes, and 14 out of 33 participants agreed. The interviewees also agreed on the elements of the questionnaire about partnership with international universities and effective plagiarism methods.

Figure 2: The Agreement and Strongly Agreement Data of the Ten-Items Questionnaire Survey about the Factors of PhD Programme in Pakistan

In comparison to other items in the questionnaire survey, the percent and ratio of agreement and strong agreement were substantially higher. The first item had a ratio of 10 to 3, the second item had a proportion of 8 to 20 out of 33, and the third item had a ratio of 7 to 23 out of 33. Other survey items included 10,5, 13,4,5,19,8,18,14,13,10,12,11, and 3. In light of the foregoing, the agreements and strongly agreed statements confirm that the restructuring and reorganization of our PhD programmes in Pakistan, particularly in the area of English language degrees, is necessary.

Figure 3: The Disagreement and Strongly disagreement Data of the Ten-Items Questionnaire Survey about the Factors of PhD Programme in Pakistan

As shown in Figure 3, the percentage and ratio of disagreement and strong disagreement were significantly lower than the percentage and ratio of agreement and strong agreement. Disagreement and strong disagreement were 7,8, in item 2, 1, 2, in item 3, 6, each item four, in item 5, 5 and 8, in item 6, 1 and 4, in item 7, only 2 strongly disagreed and 3 disagreed, in item 9, only 5 disagreed and 2 strongly disagreed, and in item 10, the percentage of disagreement was greater than the other disagreed statements.

Results and Discussion

The findings of this research study show that most of the problems that our PhD programs specially PhD in English have are due to the factors mentioned in the research questionnaire. Most of the respondents agreed that the ten issues are the constant roadblocks to quality assurance in doctorate programmes taught in English. If quality is to be maintained, they must be addressed immediately. All of these difficulties can be found practically in most of the Pakistan's public and private universities. To cope with these issues, some cogent and practical steps are necessary and the proposed remedial steps would decrease the intensity of the issues. For this to happen, the Higher Education Commission of Pakistan should not only provide funds and grants but a strict monitoring system should be introduced to check the performances of the universities.

The research at PhD level must be at par with the international level and such researches should be tested and examined at worldwide forums. They must be founded on our most pressing issues, and this research must also help to alleviate these issues in order to ensure quality at academic levels, particularly in doctoral degrees such as the Ph.D. in English. Only by bringing Pakistani English degrees up to international norms and levels can achieve greatness.

Conclusion

The findings of this research study show us that there are issues in our PhD programs and especially in English PhD program in Pakistan. However, in comparison to other science disciplines and social sciences, the PhD program in English is the most affected one and this discipline of humanities needs aggressively corrective measures and action to address the slew of issues within this program. HEC is also making every effort to improve the quality of indigenous Ph.D. programmes. The quality of Ph.D. in English can be improved substantially only if its quality assurance is made sure and all issues and problems are addressed.

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